

SPECIAL ISSUE ARTICLE

Low-temperature sintered boron-doped S53P4 bioactive glass scaffolds fabricated by robocasting

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Abstract

This study investigates boron-doped S53P4 bioactive glass (BG) scaffolds fabricated via robocasting in the context of bone regeneration strategies by comparing their mechanical performance and bioactive behavior to undoped S53P4 BG scaffolds. Three-dimensional scaffolds with grid-like macro architectures were fabricated using gelatin-based composite inks containing S53P4 BG and 10 wt.% boron-doped S53P4 BG (S53P4_10B). The scaffolds were sintered at optimized temperatures (900°C for S53P4 and 615°C for S53P4_10B), resulting in an average volumetric shrinkage of 33 vol%. Both scaffold types exhibited high porosity (~71%) with pore sizes of $584 \pm 7 \mu\text{m}$ (S53P4) and $608 \pm 25 \mu\text{m}$ (S53P4_10B). Compressive strength values of $3.3 \pm 1.7 \text{ MPa}$ and $1.5 \pm 0.4 \text{ MPa}$ were respectively measured for S53P4 and for S53P4_10B BG scaffolds. Soaking in simulated body fluid for 14 days resulted in complete surface coverage with calcium-phosphate-rich phases, indicating high bioactivity. Antibacterial tests revealed that while crystallization reduced the inhibition zone of S53P4 scaffolds, S53P4_10B scaffolds exhibited significant antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Cytocompatibility tests using MG-63 and ST-2 cell lines confirmed that scaffold extracts at concentrations $\leq 1\%$ w/v were noncytotoxic. These results show that boron-doped BG scaffolds possess bioactivity, antibacterial efficacy, and cytocompatibility, and suggest that their mechanical performance can be further tuned through scaffold design and sintering conditions.

KEYWORDS

bioactive glass, bone-regeneration, robocasting, scaffold, S53P4

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1 | INTRODUCTION

When the width of a bone defect surpasses the critical threshold (as a guideline: 1–2 cm), spontaneous healing cannot occur, and thus, bone grafting is necessary.¹ Bone grafting is a surgical procedure that includes different materials, such as autografts, allografts, or synthetic biocompatible materials, to treat diseased or damaged bones through transplantation.² Autografting involves harvesting tissue from the patient's body, eliminating the risk of immune rejection, and ensuring high compatibility. This technique is considered the gold standard for grafting due to the graft's inherent osteogenic, osteoinductive, and osteoconductive properties. However, autografts are associated with significant limitations. The need for a second surgical site increases operative time, blood loss, and the risk of complications such as infection, pain, and donor-site morbidity. Additionally, the limited availability of donor tissue restricts its use in cases requiring large volumes of graft material. These drawbacks highlight the need for alternative solutions to address the challenges of tissue availability and surgical complexity.^{2–4} Allografting is an alternative technique based on organ or tissue transplantation from a donor or cadaver. However, its practicability is suppressed due to difficulties such as cost and the risk of rejection.^{2,5,6} Hierarchical porous synthetic three-dimensional (3D) scaffolds designed for tissue engineering (TE) can mimic the functions of the extracellular matrix in bone tissue and address the limitations of known grafting approaches.^{7,8} TE scaffolds provide an environment for cells to attach, migrate, and differentiate. The inherent structure and function of the defective region are thus restored.⁹ The cellular activity within a scaffold largely depends on its architecture and the chemical composition of the used material. Calcium sulfate, tricalcium phosphate, and hydroxyapatite (HA) are commonly employed in scaffold applications due to their ability to effectively osseointegrate with bone tissue.¹⁰ While these materials can bind to surrounding bone tissues and promote osteoconductivity, they usually lack the ability to stimulate new blood vessel formation. This limitation in achieving successful neovascularization in tissue-engineered scaffolds can disrupt the metabolic activities of bone-related cells, potentially leading to adverse effects such as impaired bone regeneration.^{11–13}

Bioactive glasses (BGs) are widely recognised for their biocompatibility, bioactivity, and biodegradability, making them valuable in TE.¹⁴ They can stimulate vascularisation, a critical tissue regeneration requirement. Moreover, due to their osteoconductive and osteoinductive properties, BGs are extensively used in bone tissue engineering applications (BTEAs) to support bone regeneration.¹⁵ The

first BG, known as 45S5 Bioglass, was developed by Larry Hench and his team in the late 1960s at the University of Florida. Its composition (46.1 mol% SiO₂, 26.9 mol% CaO, 24.4 mol% Na₂O, and 2.6 mol% P₂O₅) allows it to form strong bonds with bone through the creation of a hydroxycarbonate apatite layer on its surface when exposed to body fluids.¹⁶ This bond is so robust that Bioglass cannot be removed without breaking the bone itself.¹⁷ Hench's discovery revolutionized biomaterials science, paving the way for other BG systems, including silicate, borate, and phosphate-based glasses, as well as formulations doped with therapeutic ions like copper and zinc to enhance biological functions such as angiogenesis and antibacterial activity.¹⁸

S53P4 BG belongs to the family of silicate-based BG systems (53 wt.% SiO₂, 4 wt.% P₂O₅, 20 wt.% CaO, 23 wt.% Na₂O).¹⁹ This formulation exhibits antibacterial properties²⁰ and promotes angiogenesis by stimulating mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) to release cytokines that induce endothelial cell differentiation and blood vessel formation.²¹ The release of pro-angiogenic cytokines, such as vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and basic fibroblast growth factor, is driven by ionic dissolution products (Ca²⁺, Si(OH)₄, and PO₄³⁻) released through ion exchange on the BG surface.^{13,22} The angiogenic response, as well as osteogenic and anti-inflammatory effects, can be further enhanced by incorporating therapeutic ions like boron (B). Boron ions (B³⁺) alter the glass network structure, increasing the degradation rate of BGs.²³ This accelerated degradation leads to a rapid pH increase in the surrounding medium, which contributes to the antibacterial activity of B-doped BGs. Considering this B-induced pH increase, the addition of B may raise concerns over elevated pH levels, whereas promoting osteogenic properties through beneficial B release is suggested to be achieved by replacing a small amount of boron oxide for SiO₂.²⁴ Additionally, the rapid glass dissolution accelerates the conversion to a HA-like phase, a phenomenon well-documented in the literature, for example, the conversion of 45S5-3B into HA within 3–4 days in simulated body fluid (SBF).²³ Another significant advantage of incorporating B into BG is its ability to enhance the glass stability value (ΔT expressed as the difference between the onset of crystallization temperature and the glass transition temperature), improving the thermal stability of scaffolds during sintering.²⁵ This increased stability allows for densification without triggering unwanted crystallization. Furthermore, scaffolds prepared with B-doped BGs exhibit improved mechanical properties,²⁶ with compressive strengths comparable to that of human cancellous bone (2–12 MPa).²⁷ Adding B₂O₃ to silica-based BGs was also reported to improve angiogenic activity and to enhance mechanical

strength, making these materials ideal for both hard and soft TE applications.^{25,28}

Various techniques, such as foam replica,²⁹ particle leaching,³⁰ and freeze-drying,³¹ can be used to fabricate a porous biomedical scaffold. While TE scaffolds fabricated through these methods meet the requirements for mimicking bone architecture (with a high porosity of $\geq 80\%$), they often fail to achieve the necessary mechanical properties.^{32,33} Robocasting, also known as direct ink writing, is an additive manufacturing (AM) technique that effectively addresses this limitation. This process involves depositing an ink onto a building platform in a controlled manner to achieve the desired grid-like scaffold structure.³⁴ Robocasting is considered the most adapted AM technique for the 3D fabrication of glass and ceramic structures due to its ease of use.³⁵ However, achieving high-quality 3D printed bodies depends heavily on the ink's rheological behavior.³⁵ The ink must exhibit shear-thinning properties, flowing easily under applied shear stress but retaining its shape once the stress is removed. Challenges such as nozzle clogging during extrusion must also be managed. Typically, inks are formulated using a selected powder, such as BG, and suitable binders, like Pluronic F-127 or gelatin. Scaffolds produced through robocasting demonstrate mechanical properties comparable to those of human cancellous bone. For example, Eqtesadi et al.³⁶ fabricated 45S5 (Bioglass) BG scaffolds with interconnected porosity ($\sim 60\text{--}80\%$), achieving compressive strength of 2–12 MPa depending on sintering conditions. Similarly, Bairo et al.³⁷ developed scaffolds using 47.5B BG, derived from the 47.5SiO₂-10Na₂O-10K₂O-10MgO-20CaO-2.5P₂O₅ (mol%) system, with 43% porosity and pore size of 150–180 μm . These scaffolds exhibited compressive strength ranging from 5.6 to 16.5 MPa in their initial state but showed a reduction in strength after immersion in SBF. Another study by Szczodra et al.³⁸ utilized boron, magnesium, and strontium-substituted BGs to fabricate scaffolds with porosities of $\sim 43\text{--}46\%$ and pore size of 277–421 μm , achieving compressive strengths of 14 MPa.

This study presents a novel ink formulation for robocasting grid-like scaffolds, utilizing S53P4 BG and B-doped S53P4_10B BG microparticles dispersed in a gelatin binder. The scaffolds were assessed for bioactivity through immersion in SBF over different periods of time. Their porosity, shrinkage, cytocompatibility, antibacterial properties, and mechanical strength were thoroughly characterized and analyzed. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that applies robocasting to process S53P4 BG doped solely with B. This innovative approach enables a direct investigation into the influence of B on the bioactivity, antibacterial efficacy, and mechanical performance of the scaffolds.

TABLE 1 The nominal compositions of the BGs denoted as S53P4 and S53P4_10B, used in this study, are presented in % (wt.).

Glass designations	SiO ₂	Na ₂ O	CaO	P ₂ O ₅	B ₂ O ₃
S53P4	53	23	20	4	–
S53P4_10B	43	23	20	4	10

2 | EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 | Materials

BGs were fabricated using high-purity ($\geq 99.95\%$) SiO₂, Na₂CO₃, CaCO₃, P₂O₅, and H₃BO₃ as raw materials. All reagents were procured from Sigma-Aldrich/Merck. The nominal compositions of BGs are given in Table 1. For ink preparation, gelatin from bovine skin, type B, was procured from Sigma-Aldrich. NaHCO₃, KCl, and NaCl used in the preparation of SBF were procured from Central Chem; the remaining consumables were procured from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2 | Synthesis and characterization of BGs

The S53P4 and 10 wt.% B-doped S53P4 (S53P4_10B) BGs were fabricated by the conventional melt quenching technique. The oxide powders were mixed on a rolling bench overnight (Phoenix Instrument, Tube Roller RS-TR 5) to ensure homogenous mixing. The mixed powders were then placed in a Pt–Au crucible and melted in an electric furnace (Clasic 0718E, Praha) at 1300°C with a heating rate of 10°C/min. The melt was held at this temperature for 2 h, during which hand mixing was performed every 15 min to ensure homogeneity. After melting, the glass was rapidly quenched by pouring the molten mixture into deionized water to form a frit. The frit was dried overnight at 100°C before being ground into fine particles using a planetary ball mill (Pulverisette 5/4, Fritsch, Idar-Oberstein) at 300 rpm for 2 h. Finally, the glass powders were sieved through a 40 μm analytical sieve (Retsch).

The particle size distribution (PSD) of the sieved BG powders was determined using a laser scattering particle size analyzer (Horiba Scientific LA-960V2, Japan), operating on static light scattering (SLS) technology. The chemical composition of the prepared glasses was verified using inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, SVDV 5100, Santa Clara). The phase analysis of the powders was conducted using X-ray powder diffraction (XRD, Malvern Panalytical Empyrean DY1098). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR, Thermo Scientific Nicolet 6700, Thermo Fisher Scientific) spectroscopy was used

to obtain basic structural information on the synthesized powders. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-7600F, Jeol) was applied to examine powder morphology. For XRD analysis, data were collected using Cu K α radiation at a voltage and current of 45 kV and 40 mA, respectively, in the 2θ range of 10° – 80° with a step of 0.02° per second using a silicon wafer as a sample holder. Phase analysis was performed using Panalytical X'Pert High Score Software. FTIR measurements were performed in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode in the wavenumber range of 400 – 4000 cm^{-1} with a 4 cm^{-1} resolution, using 40 scans. SEM images were collected at a 10.9 mm working distance and a 20 kV acceleration voltage. The thermal behavior of the glasses was characterized by simultaneous differential scanning calorimetry and thermogravimetry (DSC-TG) using an STA 449 F1 Jupiter analyzer (Netzsch) under nitrogen atmosphere, from room temperature to 1300°C . Two hundred milligrams of powder (particle size < 40 μm) was heated in a platinum crucible at a rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The DSC-TG data were analyzed using the SW Netzsch Proteus software. Heat treatment programs for the densification of prepared scaffolds were based on DSC-obtained data.

2.3 | Preparation of BG/gelatin ink and robocasting of BG scaffolds

The ink used for robocasting was prepared by mixing the BG powder with 10 wt.% gelatin solution. According to the helium pycnometer measurements (Quantachrome Ultrapyc 1200e, Anton Paar), the density values of the BGs were determined as 2.69 g/cm^3 for S53P4 and 2.63 g/cm^3 for S53P4_10B, respectively, while the density of the 10 wt.% gelatin solution was considered as 1.04 g/cm^3 .³⁹ The gelatin solution was heated up to 50°C to enable the mixing with the powder in a 0.6 mL/g liquid-to-powder ratio. After homogenization, the ink was put into a 3 mL cartridge (Optimum Syringe Barrels, Nordson EFD) and left for 15 min at 22°C to allow for physical crosslinking of the gelatin, after which the ink was ready for printing. Filaments of the scaffolds were printed out using a conical dispensing nozzle with an internal diameter of 590 μm (Precision Tips, Nordson EFD). Two geometries of BG scaffolds were produced: cubes for mechanical testing ($10 \times 10 \times 10$ mm^3) and cuboids for other characterizations ($10 \times 10 \times 4$ mm^3), all with a rectilinear pattern orthogonal in consecutive layers. The infill density of the scaffolds was set to 38%, with a theoretical distance of 1000 μm between the surfaces of the filaments. Infill overlap was set to 2% of the nozzle diameter. Scaffolds were printed out at an infill speed of 16 mm/s. After printing, the scaffolds were left to dry in air for at least 24 h. The printed S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds were heat-treated to ensure binder burnout and

sintering at maximum temperatures of 900°C and 615°C , respectively, with a dwell time of 1 h.

2.4 | Mechanical, physical, and microstructural properties

Compressive strength was evaluated using a universal testing system (Instron 3300 Floor Model, Instron GmbH). The scaffolds were subjected to compression testing in the as-sintered condition, without postprocessing such as surface cutting or polishing. The tests were conducted at a speed of 0.5 mm/min with a 30 kN load cell applying the load perpendicular to the printed layers. The initial distance was set close to the height of the scaffolds. The measurement was stopped automatically once the total compression displacement reached 30%. SEM and XRD analysis were used to perform microstructural imaging of sintered scaffolds and detect any crystalline phase formation. The conditions were identical to those employed in powder characterization (Section 2.2). The geometric density (ρ_g) of scaffolds was calculated as the weight-to-volume ratio ($\frac{m_s}{V_s}$), with weights determined using an analytical balance and dimensions measured by a digital calliper. The apparent density (ρ_A) and the true density (ρ_T) were determined using a helium pycnometer (Quantachrome Ultrapyc 1200e Automatic Gas Pycnometer, Anton Paar Group AG). The ρ_A was measured using the scaffold in its original shape, whereas for ρ_T measurement, the scaffolds were crushed into powder. The measured density values were employed to calculate the amount of total (TP%), open (OP%), and closed porosity (CP%) using Equations (1)–(3):

$$\text{TP} = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_g}{\rho_t}\right) \times 100, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{OP} = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_g}{\rho_A}\right) \times 100, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{CP} = \text{TP} - \text{OP}. \quad (3)$$

The linear ($\Delta L_{x,y,z}$ %) and volumetric (ΔV_s %) shrinkage values of the densified glass scaffolds were calculated using Equations (4) and (5):

$$\Delta L_{x,y,z} (\%) = \frac{L_i - L_f}{L_i} \times 100, \quad (4)$$

where L_i represents the initial external length of the green scaffold and L_f denotes the final length of the scaffold after densification.

$$\Delta V_s (\%) = \frac{V_i - V_f}{V_i} \times 100, \quad (5)$$

where V_i suggests the initial volume of the scaffold, considering its external dimensions and V_f stands for the final volume.

2.5 | In vitro bioactivity

The bioactivity of 3D-printed S53P4 and S53P4_10B cuboid scaffolds ($10 \times 10 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$) was evaluated in vitro in terms of forming a HA-like rich layer on the surface by immersing in SBF. The SBF solution was prepared based on the Kokubo method.⁴⁰ The experiment was conducted in a $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ orbital shaker incubator (Shaking Incubator 69L ZWYR-200D, Labwit Scientific) at 120 rpm for 1, 7, and 14 days. As suggested by Macon et al.,⁴¹ the scaffold mass to SBF volume ratio was kept constant at 1.5 mg/mL. The SBF solution was refreshed every two days to maintain ionic stability, with pH measured at each refresh; overall pH changes were studied by measuring the SBF supernatant at 37°C on assay days 1, 7, and 14 using a pH meter (Mettler Toledo). After immersion, scaffolds were rinsed three times with deionized water to remove residual SBF and dried overnight in a furnace at 60°C . The dried scaffolds were ground into powder for XRD and FTIR analyses to verify HA formation. SEM was employed to examine scaffold morphology. Details of the applied characterization parameters are provided in Section 2.2.

2.6 | Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial activity was assessed using the agar diffusion assay (direct method) against Gram-negative (*E. coli*) and Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) bacterial strains. Luria/Miller agar and lysogeny broth (LB) medium (Carl Roth GmbH, Karlsruhe) were used for bacterial culture. Both strains were incubated in 10 mL of LB medium at 37°C for 24 h. The optical density of the bacterial suspension was measured at 600 nm using a Genesys 30 spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific); the bacterial concentration (optical density) was maintained at 0.020 ± 0.005 . Separately, 20 mL of agar solution (agar and LB medium) was poured into a plastic Petri dish (agar plate) and left to solidify. Afterwards, 20 μL of each bacterial suspension was evenly spread over the surface of the agar plates.

The scaffolds S53P4 and S53P4_10B were ground into fine powders, and 200 mg of each group was pressed into pellets using an 11 mm diameter die with the applied force of 25 kN. The pellets were sterilized by dry heat sterilization at 160°C for 2 h. The prepared pellets were then placed in the center of the agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The zone of inhibition (ZOI) around each pellet was measured using ImageJ software (version 1.54d,

NIH, Bethesda). The ZOI was calculated using Equation (6):

$$\text{Zone of inhibition (mm)} = \frac{\varnothing_1 - \varnothing_2}{2}, \quad (6)$$

where $\varnothing_1 = (2R + \varnothing_2)$ represents the diameter of the inhibition zone, and \varnothing_2 is the diameter of the prepared pellets.

2.7 | In vitro cell viability

The cytocompatibility of the scaffolds was evaluated using MG-63 (osteosarcoma) and ST-2 (stromal) cells in accordance with ISO 10993-5:2009. Scaffolds were ground into powder form and sterilized in an oven at 120°C for 3 h (ED 56, Binder GmbH). A suspension (stock solution) was prepared by mixing 100 mg of scaffold powder in 1 mL (10% w/v) of Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM) and Roswell Park Memorial Institute Medium (RPMI), both containing 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS, Sigma-Aldrich) and 1% (v/v) penicillin/streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich), in accordance with ISO 10993-12:2012. The suspension was incubated at 37°C for 24 h, followed by centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 5 min (Eppendorf 5453 Minispin Plus Centrifuge). The supernatant was collected for further testing. MG-63 and ST-2 cells were seeded into a 96-well plate at a concentration of 5000 cells/well and incubated at 37°C in a 5% CO_2 atmosphere for 24 h. The collected supernatant was then added to the 96-well plates (200 μL), with DMEM-based supernatant used for MG-63 cells and RPMI-based supernatant used for ST-2 cells. The supernatant was also diluted to 1, 0.1, and 0.01% w/v and placed with the cells. The cells were further incubated for 24 h. Control wells contained only DMEM or RPMI without scaffold powder extracts.

After 24 h of incubation with the scaffold supernatants, cell viability was assessed using the WST-8 assay (CKK-8 kit, Abcam). Cells were washed with Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (Gibco Life Technologies, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Schwerte), and 200 μL of a 1% (v/v) WST-8 solution in either DMEM or RPMI was added to each well. The plates were incubated for an additional 4 h at 37°C . Optical density (OD) was measured at a wavelength of 450 nm using a spectrophotometer (BioTek Epoch). The relative cell viability (%) was calculated using Equation (7):

$$\text{Relative cell viability (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Sample}_{\text{absorbance}} - \text{Blank}_{\text{absorbance}})}{(\text{Control}_{\text{absorbance}} - \text{Blank}_{\text{absorbance}})} \times 100. \quad (7)$$

FIGURE 1 Structural characterization of the prepared glasses: (A) X-ray diffraction patterns, (B) FTIR spectra.

2.8 | Statistical analysis

Mechanical tests were conducted using nine samples for each composition, while biological experiments were performed in triplicate. Linear and volumetric shrinkage data, as well as filament diameter and pore size measurements, were collected from at least three scaffolds per group. All data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analyses included one-way and two-way analysis of variance with significance levels set at $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, and $***p < 0.001$. Pairwise comparisons between groups were performed using Tukey's post hoc test. The Tukey analysis was conducted via the Paired Comparison Plot Application in Origin 2023 software (OriginLab Corporation).

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 | Powders

ICP-OES analysis confirmed that the glass compositions matched their nominal values. Figure 1A shows the broad halo observed between 2θ 25° and 40° in the X-ray diffraction pattern, confirming the amorphous nature of the glasses. Figure 1B presents the FTIR absorbance spectra of the prepared glasses, with vibrational bands attributed to Si–O–Si stretching (1006 cm^{-1} , 911 cm^{-1}), Si–O–Si bending (755 cm^{-1} , 590 cm^{-1}), and Si–O–Si rocking (451 cm^{-1}).^{42–44} The broadband in the $1390\text{--}1510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is associated with carbonate groups within the glass structure, likely arising from atmospheric CO_2 absorption.⁴⁵ Substituting 10 wt.% B_2O_3 for SiO_2

reduces the intensity of Si–O–Si vibration bands in the FTIR spectra: this decrease becomes more significant as the boron-to-silicon substitution ratio increases.²⁵ Concurrently, new vibration bands corresponding to B–O bonds emerge. Peaks at 1417 cm^{-1} and 1197 cm^{-1} are assigned to B–O stretching vibrations in $[\text{BO}_3]$ trigonal units.^{46,47} However, distinguishing B–O vibrations from $[\text{BO}_4]$ units is challenging due to their overlap with Si–O–Si stretching vibrations.⁴⁶ The substitution also induces shifts in other vibrational bands. The Si–O–Si bending band at 755 cm^{-1} shifts to 732 cm^{-1} due to the formation of B–O–B linkages. Additionally, the band at 590 cm^{-1} disappears and is replaced by B–O–B bending vibrations around $\sim 550\text{ cm}^{-1}$.^{25,46,48} These spectral changes indicate significant structural reorganisation within the glass network as boron replaces silicon.

Figure 2 depicts the morphology and PSD of the BG powders used in this study. As both glasses were subjected to identical ball milling protocols, similar monodispersity with irregular-shaped morphology was observed. The particles had a median size (d_{50}) of 12 and 13 μm for S53P4 and S53P4_10B, respectively. The PSD of the feedstock strongly influences the flow behavior of the ink.⁴⁹ The broad PSD of the powders prevents difficulties during printing, such as particle rearrangement or slipping, caused by a narrow PSD.^{50,51} Smaller particles fill the gaps between large particles, facilitating the ink extrusion under shear forces. The SLS results (Figure 2B,D) show that S53P4 and S53P4_10B glass powders have a relatively narrow PSD linked to the applied milling protocol. This controlled PSD ensures consistent ink behavior, which is vital for achieving high-quality scaffold fabrication.

FIGURE 2 Morphology and particle size distribution of dry ball-milled glass powders: (A) S53P4 (SEM), (B) S53P4 (SLS), (C) S53P4_10B (SEM), and (D) S53P4_10B (SLS).

TABLE 2 DSC results of glasses, T_g , T_x , T_p , and ΔT stand for glass transition temperature, crystallization onset temperature, crystallization peak temperature, and glass stability value, respectively.

Glass designations	T_g	T_x	T_p	ΔT ($T_x - T_g$)
	[°C], (SD \pm 2)			
S53P4	556	659	751	103
S53P4_10B	499	620	660	121

The DSC thermograms of the prepared glasses are shown in Figure 3, while Table 2 summarizes the DSC data of the respective BGs, which agree with the literature.⁵² The addition of B_2O_3 to the glass composition results in a reduction of the glass transition temperature (T_g), a trend corroborated by a previous study.²⁵ In that study, T_g decreased gradually with increasing B_2O_3 substitution (up to 100% replacement of SiO_2), attributed to the

FIGURE 3 DSC thermograms of the prepared glasses.

progressive incorporation of boron into the network. This is in agreement with our observations at 10 wt.% doping, suggesting a similar mechanism at lower concentrations. Although the $[\text{BO}_3]$ units are strongly bonded to each other within a single boroxol ring, the interconnection bonds among boroxol rings are weak.⁵³ This phenomenon results in lower thermomechanical features in the B_2O_3 glass network, such as the T_g , correlated to the activation energy needed for structure relaxation. Besides, Xianyan et al.⁵⁴ also suggested that B_2O_3 addition balances the charge of the system, which they associated with polymerization of the silicate network and a decrease in T_g . However, the observed reduction in T_g suggests that while boron may integrate into the network as a former (e.g., BO_4 tetrahedra), its overall effect corresponds to depolymerization, likely due to weaker B–O bonds or nonbridging oxygen formation.

The glass stability value (ΔT), the difference between crystallization onset temperature and T_g , is a critical factor for thermal processing in glass applications. A higher ΔT indicates greater thermal stability and resistance to crystallization. For example, 45S5 BG has a relatively narrow ΔT of $\sim 88^\circ\text{C}$, making it prone to crystallization, a property undesirable especially for bioactivity. The S53P4 BG exhibits a wider ΔT of $\sim 103^\circ\text{C}$. These values are in close agreement with recent DSC analyses of undoped S53P4 powder, where ΔT ranged from 91°C to 112°C at heating rates of $5\text{--}20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, increasing with higher heating rates due to delayed T_x .⁵⁵ As shown in Table 2, boron doping further increases ΔT compared with the base glass. This improvement is attributed to boron's ability to disrupt the glass network, increasing disorder and reducing the glass tendency to crystallize during thermal processing. A larger ΔT is advantageous for sintering applications, allowing better control over densification while minimizing unwanted crystallization.

3.2 | Scaffolds

The optical images in Figure 4A,D,E,H illustrate sintered BG scaffolds with a grid-like macroarchitecture and a rectilinear pattern arranged orthogonally in consecutive layers. These scaffolds were fabricated using a nozzle with a $590\ \mu\text{m}$ internal diameter. The gelatin-based ink formulation containing 39%–40% (vol.) BG particles ensured structural integrity, making the scaffolds mechanically robust, which could be easily removed from the printing platform without additional processing, such as oil bathing. The structures exhibited $\sim 5\%$ linear shrinkage due to water elimination during drying. SEM micrographs in Figure 4C,G reveal the microstructure of S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds sintered at 900°C and 615°C , respec-

TABLE 3 Summary of linear (x, y, z) and volumetric (% vol.) shrinkage values of S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds.

Designations	Linear shrinkage			Volumetric shrinkage (% vol.)
	x (%)	y (%)	z (%)	
S53P4	12 ± 2	12 ± 2	11 ± 4	32 ± 5
S53P4_10B	12 ± 3	15 ± 3	14 ± 3	36 ± 3

tively. Micropores (highlighted by red arrows) seen in Figure 4C resemble those observed in previous studies of 45S5 BG-based scaffolds sintered at similar temperatures (e.g., 950°C and 900°C for 5 h).^{29,36} As described in the literature,^{56–58} glass densification occurs through viscous flow. When heated above the T_g , softened particles bond under surface tension, with densification stages governed by viscosity and pore elimination dynamics. The necking that occurs at the beginning of the sintering process is defined as the formation of bonded regions between particles during viscous flow. Figure 4G proves that the particles in the B-doped scaffolds sintered at 615°C are in the early stages of sintering. This was an anticipated outcome, given that the B-doped BG scaffolds were sintered at lower temperatures than the S53P4-based scaffolds. The decision to sinter at lower temperatures addressed a key challenge of BG-based scaffolds: preserving their amorphous nature, which is critical for maintaining or enhancing bioactivity. Moreover, both the antibacterial activity and bioactivity of a scaffold depend on the amorphous state of the glass, as its dissolution products play a crucial role in driving both phenomena.

Figure 5 presents the XRD patterns of S53P4 and S53P4_10B BG scaffolds sintered at 900°C and 615°C , respectively. As anticipated, the S53P4 scaffolds exhibited a glass-ceramic microstructure predominantly composed of combeite crystals (ICSD pdf card 96-900-7722, $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_9$).⁵² Previous studies on S53P4 BG reported two different crystalline phases, $\text{Na}_2\text{CaSi}_2\text{O}_6$ and $\text{Ca}_4\text{Na}_2\text{P}_2\text{SiO}_{12}$.⁵⁹ Notably, the $\text{Na}_2\text{CaSi}_2\text{O}_6$ crystal phase has been identified as an analogue of combeite, differing in its Na/Ca stoichiometric ratio.^{52,60} In contrast, the S53P4_10B scaffolds retained an amorphous halo within the 2θ range of 25° to 35° , although the formation of combeite phases was observed. Additionally, it has been reported that B-containing crystalline phases, such as $\text{CaNa}_3\text{B}_5\text{O}_{10}$, may form in glasses with increased B_2O_3 content.⁶¹ However, no such phases were detected in this study, likely due to the relatively low boron (B) content in the glass network and insufficient atomic rearrangement caused by the low sintering temperature applied.

Table 3 summarizes the sintered scaffolds' linear and volumetric shrinkage values. Comparable linear shrinkage results were observed in the x and y printing directions for S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds. The S53P4_10B

FIGURE 4 SEM and optical micrographs of sintered BG scaffolds: whereas (A, D) and (E, H) are optical images of the top and side view of the sintered S53P4 and S53P4_10B BG scaffolds, (B, C) and (F, G) show SEM images of the scaffolds at higher magnification, respectively.

FIGURE 5 XRD diagrams of S53P4 and S53P4_10B BG scaffolds sintered at 900°C and 615°C, respectively. The combeite (ICSD ref. code 96-900-7722, $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_9$) reference pattern is shown at the bottom of the chart.

scaffolds exhibited $\sim 4\%$ greater volumetric shrinkage than the S53P4 BG scaffolds, primarily due to increased linear shrinkage in the z -direction. However, this difference in volumetric shrinkage was insignificant ($p > 0.05$). As expected, linear shrinkage in the z -direction for both scaffold types was equal to or greater than that in the x and y directions. During thermal treatment, the decomposition of gelatin below 350°C, which acts as a binder for scaffold particles, likely created macro and microvoids. Z -direction shrinkage was primarily driven by increased filament overlap at intersections, where adjacent filaments compress into one another, rather than by gravitationally induced deflection or void formation during binder removal. In shifted scaffold designs, gravitational forces induce bending stresses on filaments, promoting densification along the z -axis.⁶² Additionally, as sintering temperatures increase, the viscous flow of the glass aids in filling smaller voids. However, early gelatin removal ($< 350^\circ\text{C}$) may result in a looser and mechanically unstable scaffold structure, as it occurs before sufficient viscous flow or atomic rearrangement begins (Table 2; 556°C for S53P4, 499°C for S53P4_10B) to densify the glass matrix.

TABLE 4 Filament diameter and pore size values of designed, printed, and sintered S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds.

Designations	Designed		As-printed		Sintered	
	Filament diameter (μm)	Pore size (μm)	Filament diameter (μm)	Pore size (μm)	Filament diameter (μm)	Pore size (μm)
S53P4	590	980	721 ± 12	658 ± 26	626 ± 34	584 ± 7
S53P4_10B	590	980	731 ± 24	669 ± 33	589 ± 27	608 ± 25

In general, it can be said that the scaffolds shrink linearly between 12% and 14% homogeneously in all printing directions. However, scaffolds in this study showing ~33% volumetric shrinkage exhibit, on average, 5%–10% higher volumetric shrinkage than the values reported in the literature.^{34,63,64}

As shown in Table 4, the as-printed filament diameters were $721 \pm 12 \mu\text{m}$ for S53P4 scaffolds and $731 \pm 24 \mu\text{m}$ for S53P4_10B scaffolds, both exceeding the nominal nozzle diameter (590 μm). The printed filaments were larger than the nozzle due to the die swelling phenomenon (Barus effect), which is well-documented in the literature.^{65–67} The gelatin-based ink is viscoelastic, so it compresses during extrusion and then elastically recovers to a larger diameter. This phenomenon also indicates that the ink had a solid-like behavior, valuable for shape retention.

After sintering, the as-printed filament diameter values decreased to $626 \pm 34 \mu\text{m}$ and $589 \pm 27 \mu\text{m}$, as shown in Table 4, due to filament densification, matching the respective linear shrinkages in the z -direction. The pore size for sintered S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds was measured as $584 \pm 7 \mu\text{m}$ and $608 \pm 25 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. On average, the pores were 100 μm larger than those in similar studies reported in the literature.^{34,36–38,63,64,68,69} The low standard deviation data indicate the repeatability and extrusion stability of the robocasting technique. The S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds exhibited total porosities of $70.7 \pm 0.9\%$ and $71.2 \pm 0.4\%$, respectively, with open porosity values of ~65% for both scaffold systems. These values fulfil the suggested porosity values for ideal vascularization and cell proliferation in a synthetic bone tissue construct.⁷⁰ The open porosity facilitates initial vascularization and nutrient diffusion in synthetic bone grafts. Although closed pores do not directly support early-stage cell migration, their gradual exposure during scaffold degradation may provide additional space for later tissue ingrowth and remodeling, thereby enhancing long-term integration.

Figure 6 compares the porosity versus compressive strength (MPa) from this study with values reported in the literature. The sintered S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds exhibited compressive strengths of $3.3 \pm 1.7 \text{ MPa}$ and $1.5 \pm 0.4 \text{ MPa}$, respectively. BG scaffolds containing 10 wt.% boron oxide were sintered at a significantly lower temperature of 615°C, just below their crystalliza-

FIGURE 6 Compressive strength (MPa) vs. porosity values from this study and literature data.

tion onset temperature (T_x , Table 2; Figure 3). Despite the reduced sintering temperature, the compressive strength of the B-containing scaffolds remains within the acceptable range for cancellous bone (2–12 MPa), demonstrating their potential for BTEAs. It has been reported that the addition of B_2O_3 to BG can enhance mechanical properties by modifying the glass network.²⁶ In this study, the lower compressive strength observed for B-containing scaffolds compared with S53P4 scaffolds (sintered at 900°C) is primarily attributed to differences in sintering conditions rather than the boron addition itself. The lower sintering temperature used for S53P4_10B scaffolds was intentionally selected to preserve their amorphous nature, which is critical for maintaining or enhancing bioactivity and antibacterial properties.

Adding boron modifies the glass network structure, altering the thermal properties of the system. Consequently, S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds cannot be sintered at identical temperatures due to their distinct thermal profiles. These differences are evident from their divergent T_g and T_x values (Table 2), which would cause uneven densification under uniform sintering conditions.

Theoretically, achieving comparable densification requires sintering each scaffold near its specific T_x value (at this point, a maximum level of densification can

theoretically be achieved while avoiding crystallization). However, Table 2 shows that this necessitates different sintering temperatures for each composition. A direct comparison under fixed conditions would require sintering S53P4 scaffolds at 615°C. DSC data demonstrate that S53P4 scaffolds need to be sintered approximately 40°C above the T_x value of S53P4_10B to ensure adequate densification. Therefore, sintering at the same temperature to observe the direct effect of densification was not implemented.

Although the compressive strength results for both scaffold types fall within the recommended range for cancellous bone (2–12 MPa),^{71,72} they are relatively lower compared with values reported in the literature (Figure 6). This discrepancy can be attributed to pore size, total porosity, and PSD, which directly affect particle packing density. The scaffolds in this study exhibited mean pore sizes of $584 \pm 7 \mu\text{m}$ and $608 \pm 25 \mu\text{m}$ for S53P4 and S53P4_10B, respectively, with approximately 71% total porosity. While pore sizes within 100–500 μm and total porosities up to 90% are considered optimal for osteogenesis,^{70,73} it is well known that increasing porosity and pore size often compromises mechanical properties.

Basam et al.⁷⁴ reported a compressive strength of 2.45 MPa for glass scaffolds with a similar pore size of 500 μm , comparable to the values observed in this study. Additionally, particle size plays a critical role in sintering. Larger particles are beneficial for maintaining an amorphous structure but lead to lower packing density, which can impair densification during sintering.³⁴ In this context, the slightly higher total porosity observed in S53P4_10B scaffolds, combined with the influence of narrow PSD on sintering behavior, likely contributed to the lower scaffold compressive strength. Furthermore, the lower filament density (resulting from reduced particle packing and lower sintering temperature) compromised individual filament strength, thereby diminishing the scaffold's overall structural integrity. Additionally, during high-temperature sintering (900°C), S53P4 scaffolds developed abundant combeite crystals, whereas S53P4_10B scaffolds retained a broad amorphous halo (2θ of 25° to 35°) with less intense combeite diffraction peaks, indicating partial crystallization. The lower degree of crystallinity in S53P4_10B scaffolds correlates with their reduced mechanical performance.

3.3 | In vitro bioactivity

The in vitro bioactivity evaluation is a crucial step in assessing the suitability of a material for use as a bone graft or bone tissue scaffold. When immersed in SBF, the formation of apatite-like crystals on the material's surface signifies its potential to form strong bonds with

FIGURE 7 Changes in pH over time for S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds immersed in SBF.

the surrounding tissue.^{15,17} The apatite-forming ability of a material is a surface-mediated phenomenon. The SBF experiment in this study was conducted using a mass-to-liquid ratio rather than a surface area-to-liquid ratio. This approach was chosen because accurately measuring the surface area of each scaffold tested was not feasible due to their complex morphology. Additionally, the protocol described by Macon et al.⁴¹ was adopted for the immersion test because it is widely used and accepted in the literature, providing a consistent basis for comparison. We acknowledge that using a mass-to-liquid ratio may influence the apatite formation results. Therefore, the findings were interpreted in the context of this limitation.

The pH changes during the SBF immersion test were monitored and are presented in Figure 7. By day 1, the pH of the S53P4 scaffold supernatant was measured at 7.52 ± 0.03 , while that of the S53P4_10B scaffold supernatant reached 7.62 ± 0.02 . The rapid pH increase for the S53P4 supernatant continued over the first 2 days, reaching 7.58 ± 0.01 , likely due to the exchange of ions such as Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , and $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ from the immersed scaffold into the SBF solution. For the S53P4_10B scaffold supernatant, the pH was recorded at 7.65 ± 0.04 , indicating a higher degree of ion release. As expected, boron incorporation accelerated scaffold dissolution during SBF immersion, as reflected in higher pH values compared with the base S53P4 scaffolds.²⁵ This is in agreement with boron's role in promoting ion exchange and rapid network hydrolysis. The sharp decrease in pH values for both scaffold supernatants at day 3 is likely due to the supernatant change one day before, which resets the leached ion saturation within the SBF solution, closely mimicking the real body environment. The upward trend in pH enhancement persisted, with pH values reaching maxima on day 5 of 7.60 ± 0.03

FIGURE 8 SEM micrographs of (A) S53P4 and (B) S53P4_10B scaffolds after immersion in SBF for 14 days. (C, E, G) and (D, F, H) show the cauliflower-like morphology of HA-like crystals formed on the surface of S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds, respectively.

for S53P4 and 7.73 ± 0.04 for S53P4_10B scaffolds. After day 5, pH values stabilized across both scaffolds, showing a slight downward trend toward ~ 7.5 by the end of the experiment. This stabilization correlates with reduced ion exchange rates, likely due to HA-like layer formation limiting scaffold–solution interactions.³⁷

SEM micrographs in Figure 8 show that both S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds were covered with apatite-like crystals after 14 days of immersion in SBF. These crystals exhibited a characteristic cauliflower-like morphology, typical of HA crystal clusters.^{25,75}

The FTIR spectra in Figure 9A,B reveal the structural groups of calcium-phosphate-rich phases formed during the bioactivity test. The absorption peaks are more prominent in the S53P4_10B scaffolds (see Figure 9B) than in the base S53P4 scaffolds (see Figure 9A) and become more visible as the immersion time increases due to the emergence of bonds related to the formation of phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) and carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) groups.

The *in vitro* bioactivity mechanism has been explained by Hench et al.¹⁷ as follows: (1) formation of a silica gel layer on the surface, (2) precipitation of an amorphous

FIGURE 9 FTIR spectra of the scaffolds with corresponding band assignments: (A) S53P4, (B) S53P4_10B after immersion in SBF for 1, 7, and 14 days.

calcium phosphate layer, (3) nucleation and growth of HA crystals. A band at $\sim 1225\text{ cm}^{-1}$ marked with a checkerboard pattern (see Figure 9A,B) increases with immersion time in both scaffolds. This band could be attributed to the formation of silica gel layer.⁷⁶ The emergence of silica gel on the scaffold surfaces matches the suggested subsequent nucleation and growth mechanism of HA-like crystals.

The C—O bonds related to the emergence of CO_3^{2-} groups in both S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffolds showed characteristic stretching absorption peaks at ~ 1460 and $\sim 1425\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and bending at $\sim 871\text{ cm}^{-1}$.^{77,78} Tetrahedral PO_4^{3-} groups in these materials exhibit ~ 600 and $\sim 560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ absorptions due to P—O bending vibrations.⁷⁹ In addition, a strong band appears at $\sim 1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$, with a shoulder at $\sim 960\text{ cm}^{-1}$, assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of P—O bonds, respectively.⁸⁰ As shown in the zoom-in part of Figure 9B, two additional bands are present at ~ 472 and $\sim 463\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the bending vibrations of the P—O bonds.⁸¹ However, the bond at $\sim 463\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is challenging to distinguish due to the presence of bands related to Si—O—Si bending vibration in the same region.²⁵ The band at $\sim 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the symmetric stretching of Si—O—Si bonds formed by the polymerization of silanol groups.^{82–86} Moreover, the intensities of bands related to B—O vibrations (see Figure 1B) decreased with increasing SBF immersion period, likely due to the release of B from the glass.^{25,83–86}

The results of the XRD analysis presented in Figure 10 reveal that the intensity of the diffraction pattern for combeite (ICSD ref. code 96-900-7722) progressively diminishes with increasing immersion time in SBF. This reduction is more pronounced in B-doped scaffolds (S53P4_10B, Figure 10B). By day 7, the XRD pattern of S53P4_10B scaffold exhibits a broad hump characteristic of amorphous phases. This feature could result from either partial or complete dissolution of combeite, reducing its density below XRD detection limits, or from precipitation of an amorphous calcium-phosphate layer that masks signals from underlying combeite crystals.⁸⁷

Although the latter hypothesis is in agreement with Hench's proposal (precipitation of an amorphous calcium-phosphate layer), the possibility of partial or complete dissolution is highly plausible. When the scaffold is ground into powder, the inner regions of particles (unaffected by SBF) are exposed, where combeite peaks should remain detectable if they had not dissolved. This argument is particularly valid if crystallization propagates from the scaffold surface toward its interior. The scaffolds were observed to undergo partial dissolution upon SBF immersion while maintaining their overall structural integrity.⁶¹ Therefore, the absence of combeite signals after grinding suggests that the combeite crystals were likely located at or near the surface and had partially or completely dissolved by day 7.

FIGURE 10 X-ray diffractograms of (A) S53P4 and (B) S53P4_10B scaffolds immersed in SBF for 1, 7, and 14 days. The crystal phases match combeite (ICSD ref. code 96-900-7722, $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_9$) and characteristic reflections of a hexagonal apatite structure, with broad diffraction maxima at $2\theta \approx 26^\circ$ and $\approx 32^\circ$, corresponding to the (002) and (112) planes.

This observation supports the dissolution of the combeite crystals, consistent with literature reports on the dissolution of $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_9$ in aqueous environments.²⁹ Overall, the results indicate that combeite dissolved effectively, leaving no detectable crystals. Detecting combeite in S53P4 scaffolds on days 7 and 14 provides significant evidence supporting its persistence. Instead, SEM and FTIR analyses confirm the formation of a calcium-phosphate apatite-like phase, while XRD data support the disappearance of combeite crystals and subsequent apatite-like phase development.

By day 14, broad diffractions emerge at $2\theta \approx 26^\circ$ and $\approx 32^\circ$, corresponding to the characteristic (002) and (112) reflections of a hexagonal apatite structure (e.g., JCPDS PDF 72-1243 for HA).⁸⁸ This transformation is further supported by SEM morphological evidence, which shows apatite-like phase deposition on the scaffold surfaces. Since crystallization is known to suppress bioactivity,⁶¹ the effective dissolution of combeite in B-doped scaffolds likely contributes to the release of bioactive ions, thereby promoting rapid apatite-like crystal phase formation.⁸⁹

3.4 | Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial efficacy of S53P4 and S53P4_10B BGs against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* bacterial strains was evaluated, and the results are presented in Figure 11. The ZOI values for S53P4 BG against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

were 0.30 ± 0.03 mm and 0.30 ± 0.02 mm, respectively, while for S53P4_10B BG, they were significantly larger at 2.6 ± 0.1 mm and 3.10 ± 0.02 mm, respectively. These results highlight the superior antibacterial performance of S53P4_10B compared with the S53P4 BG.²⁵

While the ZOI values for S53P4 BG were similar for both bacterial strains, S53P4_10B BG demonstrated greater efficacy against *S. aureus* than *E. coli*. This difference may be attributed to structural variations between Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria. Gram-negative bacteria possess a thin peptidoglycan layer surrounded by an outer membrane, which acts as a barrier to antibacterial agents. In contrast, Gram-positive bacteria lack this outer membrane, allowing easier penetration of ions.⁹⁰

The antibacterial mechanism of BGs is primarily attributed to pH increase and ion release.⁹¹ The release of alkali (Na^+) and alkaline earth (Ca^{2+}) ions from the glass, in exchange for H^+ ions in the surrounding medium, results in a rapid increase in pH, creating conditions unfavourable for bacterial survival.⁹² Additionally, the release of $(\text{BO}_3)^{3-}$ ions from borate BGs has been shown to effectively inhibit bacterial growth, as supported by previous studies.^{25,93} The efficacy of S53P4_10B BG against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus* is likely due to the release of $(\text{BO}_3)^{3-}$ ions. In contrast, while S53P4 BG is a proven antibacterial glass composition,²⁰ its crystallization appears to suppress the release of ions critical for antibacterial activity, which explains its limited ZOI values in this study.

FIGURE 11 Agar diffusion assay of S53P4 and S53P4_10B pellets after 24 h of incubation against *E. coli* (Gram-negative) and *S. aureus* (Gram-positive), showing that S53P4_10B samples exhibited significantly enhanced antibacterial activity compared with S53P4 against both bacteria ($p < 0.0001$).

3.5 | In vitro cell viability

Figure 12 shows the in vitro relative cell viability (%) of MG-63 and ST-2 cell lines incubated with scaffold powder extracts from S53P4 and S53P4_10B BGs for 24 h. The S53P4 scaffolds, sintered at 900°C, underwent nearly complete crystallization (see Figure 5), suppressing their ion release capability. As shown in Figure 12A, incubation of MG-63 cells with a 10% (w/v) S53P4 scaffold powder extract resulted in 74.7% relative cell viability, exceeding the 70% threshold for noncytotoxicity as defined by ISO 10993-5:2009 and supported by literature reports.^{94,95} In contrast, the S53P4_10B extract under identical conditions yielded only 53.1% relative cell viability, indicating potential cytotoxicity (ISO 10993-5:2009). This difference can be attributed to the incorporating B in S53P4_10B BG, which accelerates network dissolution and increases the release of ions, leading to elevated cytotoxicity in static culture conditions,^{75,96} and reduced MG-63-cell viability.^{97,98} This phenomenon may differ under in vivo conditions due to the dynamic environment with flowing fluids surrounding the scaffolds.⁹⁹ Previous studies have reported that increasing B substitution in silicate BGs leads to a proportional rise in ion release, adversely affecting cell viability.²⁵ Conversely, when $(BO_3)^{3-}$ ion concentrations remain below a critical threshold, such ions have been shown to promote cell proliferation.^{100,101} Additionally, after 24 h of incuba-

tion, the stock solution prepared with DMEM (10 w/v%) had a pH of 7.87 for S53P4 and 8.10 for S53P4_10B BGs (measured before incubation with cells). As shown previously, a similar 24 h incubation period yielded pH values of 7.52 ± 0.03 for S53P4 and 7.62 ± 0.02 for S53P4_10B in the supernatants from scaffolds immersed in SBF, supporting the previous claims. Dilution of the extracts from the initial 10% (w/v) concentration to 1%, 0.1%, and 0.01% (w/v) resulted in cell viability levels that were comparable to the control for both scaffold types, indicating reduced cytotoxicity at lower concentrations but no significant enhancement in proliferation compared with the control group. For S53P4_10B scaffolds, MG-63 cell viability at a 10% (w/v) concentration was significantly lower than that observed at diluted concentrations (1%, 0.1%, and 0.01% w/v) and in the control group ($***p < 0.001$, Figure 12A). No significant differences were observed among the diluted extracts (1%, 0.1%, and 0.01% w/v) and the control group. In contrast, for S53P4 scaffolds, significant differences were observed among groups ($*p < 0.05$ and $**p < 0.01$). For the ST-2 cell line, both S53P4 and S53P4_10B scaffold extracts (10 w/v%) showed ~30% cell viability, which indicates cytotoxicity. Indeed, when examining the ST-2 cell line at the 10% (w/v) concentration level, no statistically significant differences in relative cell viability values were observed between S53P4 and S53P4_10B extracts (Figure 12B). This result suggests that B release

FIGURE 12 In vitro relative cell viability (%) of (A) MG-63 and (B) ST-2 cell lines incubated for 24 h with extracts of 10, 1, 0.1, and 0.01 (w/v). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$ indicate statistical differences.

had a lower impact on ST-2 cell viability than in the case of MG-63 cells. However, similar to MG-63 cells, dilution of the extracts resulted in ST-2 cell viability levels that were comparable to or slightly higher than the control, although the increase was not statistically significant (Figure 12B).

Compared with the control, cell viability values are lower at 10% (w/v) concentration and higher at diluted concentrations, showing a wider fluctuation. This behavior indicates that ST-2 cells are more sensitive to ion release and cytotoxic effects than MG-63 cells. This result suggests that MG-63 osteosarcoma cells exhibit a higher tolerance to ion release. While lower B concentrations may promote cell growth in both cell lines, higher concentrations can have cytotoxic effects, as discussed before. Although the lactate dehydrogenase assay was not conducted, pre-

vious studies suggest that excessive ion release from BGs, particularly elevated levels of Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , and B^{3+} , can induce cellular stress or destabilize cell membranes, potentially contributing to reduced cell viability at higher extract concentrations.^{102,103} To validate this hypothesis further, a detailed investigation into the ion release profiles of both scaffold types is necessary.

4 | CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that optimized sintering conditions for boron-containing S53P4 scaffolds fabricated via robocasting preserved high porosity and structural integrity while maintaining desirable bioactivity and mechanical performance. The scaffolds were cytocompatible at clinically relevant dilutions, providing a solid platform for future architectural and surface-engineering optimizations toward regenerative medicine applications. Boron doping enhanced antibacterial properties, effectively inhibiting *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, while maintaining a balance between mechanical stability and bioactivity. The boron-containing scaffolds' compressive strengths fell within the acceptable range for cancellous bone, suggesting potential for further mechanical optimization through adjustments in sintering conditions or scaffold architecture. Future research should focus on optimizing boron concentrations and exploring combinations with other therapeutic ions to enhance mechanical properties and biological performance.

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